

Multifunctional Polyurethane-enhanced Buckypaper Sheets based on Carbon Nanotubes and Boron Nitride Nanotubes

Behnam Ashrafi^{1*}, Yadienka Martinez-Rubi², Michael B. Jakubinek², Kurits Laqua¹,
Daesun Park¹, Shan Zou³, Keun Su Kim², Ali Yousefpour¹, Benoit Simard²

Aerospace Portfolio, National Research Council Canada, 5145 Decelles Av., Montreal, QC, H3T 2B2, Canada

²Security and Disruptive Technologies Portfolio, National Research Council Canada, 100 Sussex Dr., Ottawa, ON, K1A 0R6, Canada

³Measurement Science and Standards, National Research Council Canada, 100 Sussex Dr., Ottawa, ON K1A 0R6, Canada

*Corresponding Author: B. Ashrafi (behnam.ashrafi@nrc-cnrc.gc.ca)

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ABSTRACTS

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) both possess low density, nanotube geometry and a range of properties that make them attractive for the fabrication of nanotube (NT) polymer composites. NT/polyurethane composite sheets were fabricated by a scalable, one-step filtration method from a suspension of polyurethane (TPU)-modified nanotubes. The approach provides for fabrication of composite with high NT-content, which is advantageous to better-leverage the properties of NTs, and the composition of the resulting NT/TPU composite sheets can be controlled through proper selection of the processing conditions. Hence materials with tailorable properties (*e.g.*, porosity, density, stiffness, toughness) can be readily produced by this method. A comparative study of the influence of BNNTs and CNTs on the tensile, electrical and mechanical properties of NT/TPU composite sheets was undertaken. In addition to studying mechanical and electrical enhancement, thermo-electrical response, strain sensing, and Joule heating capabilities were also investigated. The high content of CNTs within TPU provides a robust network, which results in an ability to detect strains above 100% (vastly more than the <5% for metallic strain gauges) with a response that is more linear than traditional conductive polymer composites. The TPU/CNT sheets are also able to detect temperature changes and sense thermal-related damage. The combination of mechanical strength, light weight, porosity, and other functionalities shows promise for several multifunctional applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Both carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) possess low density, nanotube geometry, high stiffness and high strength, as well as complimentary electrical, optical and thermal properties, making them attractive for multifunctional enhancement of polymers. Development of multifunctional materials based on CNTs is widely examined in literature [1-2]. In particular, CNTs are electrically conductive and are most-commonly employed in composites to improve the electrical conductivity of a matrix. In the case of BNNTs, their higher thermal stability, wide band gap leading to lack of absorption in the visible spectrum and high electrical resistance, and high neutron absorption capability offer promise to develop multifunctional composites for applications where CNTs are not ideal or are unsuitable [3,4].

Direct mixing of nanotubes (NTs), for both cases of CNTs and BNNTs, into polymers results in composites containing low content of NTs (often <5 wt%) due to processing challenges such as NT agglomeration. In this study, we prepare high content thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) nanocomposite sheets (similar to buckypaper sheets) using a novel one-step filtration process that provides tailorable NT:TPU ratios [5]. TPU is among the most versatile polymers today, consisting of

hard and soft segments which can be tailored to meet desired properties. The mechanical properties can also be tailored through controllable void, NT and TPU content. For conductive CNT/TPU composites, the nanocomposite sheet has electrical conductivity above 1,000 S/m and can reach over 200% strain, making this material suitable for various applications combining structural properties and electrical response (*e.g.*, electro-responsive materials). In addition to studying mechanical and electrical enhancement, we have studied the electromechanical response for environmental sensing, strain sensing, and joule heating capabilities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Material Development

Commercially available multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs; Nanocyl® NC7000TM, Belgium) were used for production of CNT/TPU buckypapers. The BNNT material was manufactured in-house, using an induction thermal plasma technique [5,6], and was purified using thermal and solvent treatments. The thermoplastic ester-based polyurethane (TPU), sold as a film adhesive product UAF 472, was supplied by Adhesive Films, Inc. In the one-step filtration method TPU and NTs were mixed in a solvent/non-solvent mixture with bath sonication. This suspension was filtered through a PTFE filter membrane with an average pore diameter of 1.2 μm . After filtration, the composite was sandwiched between sheets of parchment and dried at room temperature overnight.

2.2 SEM and AFM Characterization

The TPU-NT buckypapers were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Hitachi High Technologies S-4700) imaging. Atomic force microscopy imaging and modulus mapping were carried out using the MultiMode AFM with the NanoScope V controller (Bruker Nano Surfaces Division, Santa Barbara, CA, USA) in Peak Force QNM mode. The peak force with which the tip taps the sample surface was kept at the lowest stable imaging level (200 – 400 pN). Silicon nitride ScanAsyst-Air AFM probes (Bruker AFM Probes, Camarillo, CA, USA) were used in all peak force feedback measurements. The manufacturer-specified typical tip diameter and spring constants are 2 nm and 0.4 N/m respectively. While images of sizes of up to 20 \times 20 μm^2 were acquired to insure good homogeneity of the nanotube networks, all the images used to measure modulus were 500 nm \times 500 nm² in size, acquired with the 512 \times 512 pixel resolution, and the AFM probe cantilever was vertically oscillated at 2 kHz and at a lateral scan rate of 1 Hz. In this way the lateral pixel size is approximately 1 \times 1 nm². The elastic modulus values were analyzed in terms of the distribution of Derjagin-Muller-Toropov (DMT) moduli over the investigated area. In order to obtain reliable results of mechanical properties through AFM, a “relative calibration method” was adopted; details about the “relative method” can be found in the instrument manual provided by Gojzewski et al. [8]. Two reference samples were selected for calibration: polystyrene and polydimethylsiloxane gel with elastic modulus of 2.7 GPa and 3.5 MPa, respectively. The calibration was carried out before all measurements of the samples characterized.

2.3 Mechanical Testing

A micro-tensile test frame (Fullam Substage Test Frame) was utilized for obtaining mechanical properties. Tensile testing was performed using free-standing rectangular specimens under tension until failure using a displacement rate of 5 mm/min.

2.4 Electromechanical Testing

Electro-mechanical testing was performed by sandwiching the CNT/TPU specimen and a copper film (an electrode) between two insulating sandpapers under the clamps of the micro-tensile test frame (Fullam Substage Test Frame). The copper electrodes were connected to a source-measure unit

(Keithley 2635A) to measure resistance at a constant voltage of 0.25 V, and then the samples were tested until failure.

2.5 Thermal-Electrical Testing

2.5.1 Joule Heating Test

Joule-heating experiments were done on 30×20 mm rectangular samples with silver paint (DuPont 4929N) attached as electrodes. A Source-measure unit (Keithly 2635A) was used to increment the voltage by 0.5 V at intervals of 100 seconds until 9 V or visible material degradation was reached. An infrared camera (FLIR SC8000 HS) was used to monitor the sample temperature.

2.5.2 Resistance-Temperature Test

Samples of 2×30 mm were cut into rectangular strips and a conductive silver paint (DuPont 4929N) was used to apply electrodes at both ends of each sample. The resistance-temperature measurement were done by placing the sample in a convection oven, heating the sample to the testing temperature, and then cooling back down to 30°C for two cycles. A constant voltage of 0.25 V was applied using a source-measure unit (Keithley 2635A) while measuring current, and a wireless thermocouple connected to data acquisition software (TC central) was used to monitor the temperature.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 NT/TPU Composite Material

Photographs of typical BNNT-TPU and CNT-TPU composite buckypaper sheets are shown in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b, respectively, demonstrating the flexibility of both composites. Partial transparency of a typical BNNT-TPU is demonstrated in Fig. 1c as compared to opaque CNT-TPU nanocomposites (Fig. 1d). Cross-sectional SEM images of BNNT-TPU and CNT-TPU are also shown in Fig. 1e and Fig. 1f, respectively. Also can be seen, both NT-TPU sheets represent a micro-structure similar to pristine, permeable nanotube buckypaper sheets.

Figure 1. Photographs and SEM images of NT-TPU composite buckypaper sheets: demonstration of flexibility of (a) CNT- and (b) BNNT-based TPU sheets; demonstration of optical transparency of (c) BNNT-TPU versus opaque (d) CNT-TPU; Cross-sectional SEM of (e) BNNT-TPU and (f) CNT-TPU.

3.2 Mechanical and Electrical Properties

The properties of both BNNT-TPU and MWCNT-TPU composite buckypapers are presented in Table 1, along with comparison to pristine buckypaper sheets and neat TPU. Both pristine buckypaper sheets displayed similar properties (void content ~80%; ultimate strength ~ 1-2 MPa; failure strain ~ 1-1.5%). The mechanical properties (for all nanocomposites) and electrical conductivity (only for CNT-TPU samples) can be tailored by changing the ratio of TPU:NTs. Similarly, the level of porosity can be tailored.

Table 1. Properties of NT-TPU Nanocomposites. (Numbers in parenthesis indicate the NT:TPU weight ratio in final composites.)

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Vol% NT	Void (%)	E (MPa)	ϵ fail (%)	σ (S/m)
Neat TPU	1.19	0	-	60±10	660	<10 ⁻¹²
CNT buckypaper	0.27	16	84	150±60	1.6±0.3	2600
BNNT buckypaper	0.37	19	81	600±100	1.0±0.2	<10 ⁻¹²
CNT: TPU (55:45)	0.57	-	63	575±89	39±9	2500
CNT: TPU (48:52)*	0.68	19	51	600±90	35±5	3100
CNT: TPU (45:55)	0.29	-	55	630±87	44 ± 4	2400
CNT: TPU (35:65)	0.81	-	32	1270±230	41±2	2300
CNT:TPU (20:80)	1.06	12	16	310±50	180±20	1000
BNNT:TPU (80:20)	0.67	28	61	2230 ± 230	6.4±1.2	<10 ⁻¹²
BNNT:TPU (40:60)	1.23	39	20	1950 ±100	82±30	<10 ⁻¹²

3.2 Atomic Force Microscopy

Peak Force QNM mode atomic force microscopy (AFM) was conducted on CNT/TPU composites and pure TPU in order to correlate experimental tensile tests (macroscale) with the elastic modulus at the nano/microscale. Modulus maps for neat TPU and CNPU(55:45) are shown in Figure 2a and b, respectively. Polyurethane elastomers are a broad family of segmented block copolymers consisting of hard crystalline segments (HS) dispersed between flexible amorphous segments (FS). The unmodified TPU (Figure 2a) clearly shows well-separated phases in the form of ribbon-like hard domains dispersed in the FS phase matrix. The modulus profile (Figure 2c) for neat TPU shows a relatively narrow elastic modulus distribution (from 9 to 100 MPa) with maximum at 59 MPa. CNPU composites show a more broad distribution from 9 to 460 MPa and 9 to 250 MPa for CNPU(55:45) and CNPU(35:65), respectively. The trend of increasing Young's modulus with increasing TPU content at the macroscale (Table 1) was not entirely observed by AFM. Although both CNPU composites show higher effective modulus than the unmodified TPU (Figure 2c, maximum at 220 MPa and 100 MPa for CNPU(55:45) and CNPU(35:65), respectively), CNPU(35:65) shows a lower value than CNPU(55:45). Additionally, the results obtained from uniaxial macroscopic tensile tests are significantly higher than those determined by AFM. It is worth pointing out that the AFM measurements were carried out on the surface of the films and only reflected the elastic modulus of the surface portion of the samples. More experiments are being conducted to better understand these results.

Figure 2. DMT modulus maps of (a) TPU, (b) CNPU(55:45), and (c) distributions of DMT modulus analyzed from the respective modulus maps for TPU, CNPU(55:45) and CNPU(35:65).

3.4 Electromechanical Response

The electromechanical response of CNT-TPU buckypaper (80:20) is also presented in Fig. 3, in which the normalized resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) is plotted as a function of strain. The sensitivity of the material is characterized by the gauge factor (GF), which can be calculated using equation 1:

$$GF = \frac{\Delta R}{R_0 \varepsilon} = (1 + 2\nu) + \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0 \varepsilon}, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta R/R_0$ is the change in resistance, ε is mechanical strain, ν is Poisson's ratio, and $\Delta \rho/\rho_0$ is change in resistivity. The film is able to sense strains above 60% with remarkably linear response ($GF \sim 1.9$), superior to dispersed CNT-TPU nanocomposites [7], which is presumed to be due to the robust conductive network formed by the buckypaper morphology and high concentration of conductive nanotubes.

Figure 3. Electromechanical response of CNT/TPU up to 120% strain.

Fig. 4 presents the strain sensing capabilities of CNT TPU under 1% and 5% cyclic strains. For the 1% cyclic strain case, there was a higher amount of recoverable strain compared to the 5% cyclic strain case, most likely due to a smaller amount of plastic deformation. In both cases the resistance peaks started to stabilize and showed repeatable behavior after the fifth cycle.

Figure 4. Electromechanical response of CNT TPU at (a)1%, (b)5% cyclic strain

3.5 Joule Heating Capability

Fig. 5a demonstrates the Joule heating capability of a 2×3 cm sheet of CNT-TPU buckypaper (80:20), and Fig. 5b shows the relationship of temperature as a function of power density. The sheet was successfully able to achieve uniform surface temperatures above 250 °C.

Figure 5. Demonstration of Joule heating capabilities of CNT TPU. (a) IR photo of CNT TPU sample up to 175°C, and (b) Temperature vs power density (per area) graph of CNT TPU

3.6 Resistance-Temperature Behavior

Figure 6 shows the cyclic thermal-electrical response of the 20:80 CNT/TPU up to 100°C and 120°C. Following initial exposure to elevated temperature, the material showed repeatable cyclic behavior. However, a permanent change occurred with additional heating beyond 100°C temperature. This indicates that, with suitable pre-conditioning, material can be used as a resistance thermometer in addition to providing a heat source.

Figure 6. Cyclic temperature dependency to 100°C, and then 120°C

4. CONCLUSIONS

A one-step infiltration process was employed to fabricate porous TPU/NT buckypaper sheets. The properties of the NT-TPU composite buckypapers were adjusted by varying the weight ratio of NTs to TPU. For CNT-TPU sheets, high CNT content provides a robust network resulting in an ability to detect strains above 100% (vastly more than the <5% for metallic strain gauges) with a response that is more linear than traditional conductive polymer composites. The CNT-TPU sheets are also able to generate heat and reach temperatures above 250°C. Additionally, the CNT-TPU showed repeatable temperature dependence, making it suitable both as a heat source and for temperature monitoring. The fabrication approach is also applicable for BNNT composite sheets. BNNT-TPU composites offer a similar range of structural properties with electrical insulation and are semi-transparent, which is different from CNT-TPU sheets and may offer additional applications alone or in combination with the CNT-TPU material.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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